

CITIZENS FOR SUSTAINABLE OLIVE OIL PRODUCTION (SOLIVEO)

QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE PRIMARY DATA

1. A SURVEY-BASED ANALYSIS OF OLIVE OIL CONSUMPTION HABITS AND SUSTAINABILITY AWARENESS

Introduction

Understanding consumer behaviour and sustainability awareness is vital for developing strategies to promote environmentally friendly practices and support local production. This report examines olive oil consumption habits and sustainability awareness, using data collected through fieldwork conducted by students from Bozdoğan Anatolian High School and Üsküdar Selimiye Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School, key contributors to our project as citizen scientists.

The analysis focuses on demographic characteristics of participants, their awareness of sustainable food concepts, olive oil consumption preferences, and factors influencing their purchasing decisions. The insights gained from the survey responses of **171 participants** aim to inform olive oil producers, policymakers, and academics, offering a foundation for targeted strategies that enhance sustainability and consumer engagement.

1. Demographic Information

Graph 1: Distribution of Participants by Gender

This graph illustrates the gender distribution of the survey participants. According to data, out of the total 171 respondents, **45 are male, while 126 are female**. This indicates a significantly higher participation rate among female respondents in the study.

Graph 2: Distribution of Participants by City of Residence

This graph displays the distribution of participants based on their city of residence. A total of **13 cities** are represented in the survey, with the highest number of participants residing in **Istanbul (83)**, followed by **Aydın (43)** and **Kocaeli (21)**. The data highlights a significant concentration of participants from these three cities. In addition to their current city of residence, participants represent 45 different hometowns, with the Aydın region being the most prominent, accounting for 40 participants.

Graph 3: Income Distribution of Participants

This graph illustrates the distribution of participants across various income levels. Among the 171 respondents, a total of **136 participants** have an income level within the range of **0–49,999 TL**. The highest number of participants (56) fall within the 0–19,999 TL bracket, followed by 53 participants in the 30,000–49,999 TL bracket, and 27 participants in the 20,000–29,999 TL bracket. The remaining income levels show fewer participants, reflecting a significant concentration in the lower income categories.

2. Findings

2.1 Olive Oil Consumption Habits

Graph 4: Olive Oil Consumption Status of Participants

This graph represents the olive oil consumption status of the survey participants. Out of 171 respondents, the majority (159 participants) reported consuming olive oil, while only 12 participants stated that they do not consume it. This indicates a very low rate of non-consumption among the participants.

- **Types of Olive Oil Consumed:** Natural olive oil is the most preferred type among participants, followed by Riviera and refined olive oil.
 - A total of 124 participants consume natural olive oil at least once a week,
 - 109 of these participants also consumed butter at a similar frequency,
 - 37 of these participants also consumed hazelnut oil at a similar frequency,
 - 70 of these people also consumed cornflower/sunflower/canola oil at a similar frequency,
 - 44 of these people also consumed margarine oil at a similar frequency,
 - The number of participants consuming Riviera olive oil at least once a week is 58,
 - The number of participants consuming refined olive oil at least once a week is 54,

was observed.

- **Sources of Supply:** Olive oil is primarily obtained from family production or local producers. Supermarkets, however, follow closely as the second most common source.
 - Among the 159 responses, 40 participants indicated sourcing their olive oil from family or familiar producers, 39 participants reported purchasing it directly from supermarkets (such as Komili, Tariş, or Sızma), and 32 participants stated that they we produce ourselves.

Graph 5: Factors Influencing Olive Oil Preferences

- **Preference Criteria:** This graph illustrates the factors participants consider when purchasing olive oil. Quality emerges as the most significant factor, selected by 131 participants, followed by organic certification (67 participants) and production location (61 participants). Price (59 participants) and brand (51 participants) also play notable roles, while packaging (26 participants) is the least prioritized factor. These findings highlight the importance of quality and certifications in shaping consumer preferences.

2.2 Awareness of Sustainability

- The majority of participants indicated that they are familiar with the concept of Sustainable Food and have adopted behaviours that support environmental sustainability.
 - In response to the statement, *I am familiar with the concept of 'Sustainable Food' (food that is environmentally friendly, ecologically balanced, and beneficial to personal health)*, 144 out of 171 participants selected the options Strongly Agree, Agree, or Slightly Agree.
- It has been observed that individuals who consume olive oil show greater interest in sustainability concepts and demonstrate higher levels of awareness.
 - Among the 159 participants who stated that they consume olive oil, the number of people who stated that they know the concept of sustainable food is 135.

2.3 Concentrations by Demographic Variables

Graph 6: Olive Oil Consumption by Gender

- Gender:** This graph illustrates olive oil consumption rates among participants based on gender. Among female participants, **92% consume olive oil, while 8% do not.** In comparison, **96% of male participants consume olive oil, with only 4% reporting non-consumption.** These findings indicate a high level of olive oil consumption across both genders, with slightly higher rates among men.

Graph 7: Education Levels of Participants

- Education:** The majority of participants are high school graduates, accounting for 37% (63 out of 171) of the respondents. This is followed by participants with primary school education (16%, 27 participants), middle school education (15%, 25 participants), and those who completed a 2- or 3-year college program (13%, 23 participants). Similarly, participants with a 4-year university or higher education degree also make up 13% (23 participants). A smaller percentage hold a master’s degree or above (5%, 8 participants), and only 1% (2 participants) reported having no formal education. This distribution demonstrates that high school graduates form the majority while participants with primary school, middle school, college, and university education levels are evenly represented.

Graph 8: Olive Oil Consumption by Education Level

This graph illustrates the relationship between education level and olive oil consumption. Olive oil consumption rates are consistently high across all education levels.

- Among high school graduates, 90% consume olive oil, while 10% do not.
- For participants with primary school education, 93% consume olive oil, and 7% do not.
- Middle school participants show slightly lower consumption, with 88% consuming olive oil and 12% not consuming it.
- Participants with a 2- or 3-year college education report a 96% consumption rate, with only 4% not consuming olive oil.
- Participants with a 4-year university degree or higher, as well as those with a master's degree or no formal education, show 100% consumption rates.

A slight positive correlation is observed between higher education levels and increased olive oil consumption.

Graph 9: Natural Olive Oil Consumption by Income Level

- **Income:** This graph illustrates the relationship between income levels and the frequency of natural olive oil consumption, focusing on participants who consume it 2–3 times a week or daily:
 - The natural olive oil consumption rate of participants with an income between 0–69,999 TL is approximately 60%, consuming it 2–3 times a week or daily.
 - The natural olive oil consumption rate of participants with an income of 150,000 TL or above is 100%, consuming it 2–3 times a week or daily.

2.4 Hometown and Consumption Habits

- Although consumption frequency and type preferences vary across hometowns, the demand for natural olive oil remains significantly high.

Graph 10: Relationship Between Olive Oil Consumption and Awareness of Healthy Food Choices

2.5 Relationship Between Olive Oil Consumption and Sustainability

- This graph explores the relationship between olive oil consumption and the ability to distinguish between healthy and unhealthy foods. Among the participants, 159 consume olive oil, while only 12 do not. Additionally, 49 participants reported that they can differentiate between healthy and unhealthy food options, compared to 11 who cannot.

These findings indicate a positive relationship between olive oil consumption and awareness of healthy eating habits. Individuals who consume olive oil tend to be more

knowledgeable about health-conscious and environmentally sustainable food practices.

3. Conclusions

The findings of this study highlight the interconnectedness of olive oil consumption habits with demographic, economic, and sustainability-related factors. By examining participants' preferences and behaviours, several key insights have emerged, providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing olive oil consumption. These insights are summarized below:

1. Olive oil consumption supports both healthy dietary habits and environmental awareness among individuals.
2. Variables such as income level and place of residence have a greater impact on olive oil consumption compared to gender or education level.
3. Awareness of sustainability demonstrates a significant relationship with olive oil consumption.
4. The rate of sourcing olive oil from local producers is considerably high.
5. Quality is the most important factor influencing olive oil preferences. Price, brand, production location, and organic certification follow with similar levels of importance, while packaging is the least prioritized factor.

4. Recommendations

1. **Sustainability Campaigns:** Organize impactful campaigns highlighting the environmental and health benefits of olive oil to raise public awareness and encourage sustainable consumption.
2. **Targeted Efforts for Low-Income Groups:** Develop strategies to provide affordable and high-quality olive oil to lower-income households, ensuring equitable access to sustainable food options.

3. **Education and Awareness Programs:** Conduct comprehensive educational programs and seminars to enhance public knowledge about sustainability and healthy eating, fostering long-term behavioural changes.
4. **Support for Local Production:** Encourage local producers to adopt sustainable production methods by providing incentives, training, and support to ensure the alignment of local practices with global sustainability standards.

2. QUALITATIVE DATA

The interview findings can be examined under **three** main headings: sustainability, olive oil production, and olive oil consumption.

Sustainability

It can be said that farmers and consumers do not have detailed knowledge about sustainability. When sustainability is mentioned, farmers primarily focus on economic sustainability. The following interview findings support this:

Farmers' perspective on the issue:

- Sustainability means getting high yields every year.
- Sustainability is about getting the reward for your labor.
- Sustainability is achieving your production target for the year while treating the soil and water correctly.

Consumers' perspective on the issue:

Consumers, especially those in Istanbul, seem to be slightly more informed about the topic.

- Sustainable? What is that? I'm hearing it for the first time.
- Sustainability? I've never heard of that word.
- Sustainability? No, I've never heard of it.
- Today's plans should lead to more creative ideas for future generations.
- First of all, sustainability has three dimensions: economic, environmental, and social components. Considering these three basic elements equally provides a holistic approach. This opens the way to looking confidently into the future. It is about using natural resources efficiently and in a balanced way to meet the needs of current and future generations.

- Sustainability means reusing the materials we use in different ways. At least, that's how I understand it. When I think of sustainability, the first things that come to mind are the environment and nature.

Olive Oil Production

When traditional olive oil production is examined, it is seen that olive oil is often produced under non-hygienic conditions without paying attention to acid and polyphenol levels.

However, even in traditional methods, when olive oil is produced under suitable conditions, social solidarity and other cultural values come to the fore.

- We used to extract olive oil with our feet. There were special olive oil sacks. The collected olives were crushed on a stone, and the crushed pulp was pressed with warm water using our feet. Since the oil rose to the top, it was collected from there.

- Olive oil acidity and polyphenols were things we didn't know about before. We've only recently started learning about them. Most of the time, we didn't even check the acidity of the oil. Even now, many people don't know the acidity of olive oil.

- In the past, there was no such thing as early harvest. Olives were pressed until they became oily, usually around December or January. But nowadays, some farmers are paying attention and harvesting olives earlier. There's even an organic olive oil production facility established nearby. None of these existed before.

- In the old days, olive harvesting was a festive occasion, celebrated with enthusiasm. Different interpretations have been made about how this period was welcomed.

- In the past, we used to harvest olives together. There was a sense of unity, especially among close family members. We would all come together and harvest the olives. There was no need to hire laborers, and the cost was low. We supported each other; there was solidarity. Now, the cost of labor is high, and the olives don't cover the expenses.

- We used to extract olives with our feet. We would dip fresh, delicious olives in figs and eat them with pleasure. It had a unique taste.

- Especially during the fig season, it was a festive atmosphere. Everyone would move to their fields, and celebrations were held together. The fields came alive. We would chat and enjoy summer evenings together.

- Now, even my grandchildren don't come to harvest olives. Even if they come to the village, they don't go olive picking. Everything falls on us, and we've grown old. It's very difficult to harvest now.

- Nowadays, people usually harvest olives using machines that emit vibrations or with rakes. In the past, olives were harvested by hitting the branches with sticks, which damaged the olives and caused bruising. Also, things called 'sergi' (curtain) have emerged. In the past, nothing was spread under the tree; olives were collected directly from the ground. Olives from the ground were mixed with newly harvested ones, which reduced quality. Now, people are more conscious. Some separate the ground olives from the newly harvested ones and press them separately, resulting in higher quality olive oil.

- In the past, there was no such thing as irrigation. If it rained, the olives were watered, but generally, the weather was better. Now, people can irrigate their olives using drip systems and get higher yields.

- Now, new olive oil extraction machines have arrived. They give you olive oil directly without contact with the outside, in a much cleaner and faster way compared to the past.

Some problems with the new production methods have also been highlighted:

- In olive production, things like fertilizers and pesticides were not used much in the past. Now, they are more widely used, but unfortunately, sometimes they are overused.

- In olive oil extraction, there is something called 'black water.' Companies discharge this into rivers on rainy days, causing fish deaths. This is a very serious problem. The government tried to prevent it but was unsuccessful.

- When olives are pressed, pomace is produced, which is used to make 'pirina' (olive dreg) and is used as fuel. In the past, we also used these as fuel. Now, some companies do this

more professionally, but there is still not enough awareness among farmers and factories. This needs to be brought into the economy.

Some comments have also been made about the problems in factory production:

- In the factory, there are long queues. You know, olives wait in sacks under the sun or rain for several days, which reduces quality.
- There are serious doubts about the reliability of olive oil pressing facilities. Many people say their oil is stolen, but even from the same farm, you can get different amounts of oil. This is directly related to the quality of the olives and the rain. Usually, people bring olives in several batches, and depending on weather conditions and the farm's situation, the quality, acidity, and quantity of the oil can vary.
- I have acquaintances at the pressing facility. Thankfully, they don't give me a hard time. I call in advance, and they tell me what time to come. They also clean the machine before pressing my olives. The acidity of my olive oil always comes below 0.8.
- I am also a member of a cooperative, which makes things easier for us. I don't remember waiting for long. They fill olive oil under much better conditions than before.

Different comments have been made about the importance of collective production and branding:

- We need to have a cooperative. Without a cooperative, our olives are left out in the open, and we can't utilize them enough. If we had a cooperative, we would be stronger and sell our olives at better prices.
- Now, there's Milas nearby. Milas registered its olive oil with the European Union. But our Memecik olives here are much better. I don't understand how they registered those tiny olives and became a brand.
- We absolutely need to become a brand. Our olives are number one in the world, but their value is not recognized. If we become a brand, we can sell abroad, and farmers can profit

from their products. Without a brand and without being presented in nice packaging, the olives go to waste.

- Additionally, Aydın province's prominence in olive oil adulteration news negatively affects producers. They say that a group of people who cheat in production are misrepresenting the city of Aydın.

Olive Oil Consumption

Olive oil consumption varies between regions. In Bozdoğan, a significant portion of participants produce their own olive oil or obtain it directly from acquaintances, while in Istanbul, consumers generally prefer well-known olive oil brands from large supermarkets.

Bozdoğan participants:

- We produce our own olive oil. We have our own farm, and we consume a lot of olive oil.
- We don't have a farm here, but our neighbors have olive groves. We get olive oil from them; it's more reliable.

Istanbul participants:

- We usually shop at large supermarkets and prefer known brands there.
- We don't consume much olive oil, and the ones we buy are usually well-known brands.
- We have acquaintances in Balıkesir, Edremit and we get it from them. It's much more reliable.

Regional differences in oil preferences are clearly visible:

In Bozdoğan, olive oil is predominantly consumed, while in Istanbul, preferences shift towards butter and sunflower oil. The main reasons for this are the price, accessibility, and taste preferences.

- In Bozdoğan, we generally consume olive oil. We use it in everything—breakfast, cold olive oil dishes, and even meat dishes. We think it’s healthier.
- We usually use butter in rice dishes, but otherwise, we prefer olive oil.
- We are from the Black Sea region, so we mostly use butter, hazelnut oil, and corn oil. Recently, we’ve started using olive oil, but mostly in dishes like stuffed vegetables.
- Olive oil is quite expensive, so we prefer corn and sunflower oil.
- We use sunflower oil for frying. Olive oil is too expensive, and its taste is too strong for me.
- Olive oil feels too heavy for me, so I prefer refined oils.
- In our oil preferences, we usually consider cost and quality, but olive oil is quite expensive compared to other oils.

Other Consumption

It has also been particularly emphasized that olive oil is used for purposes other than cooking, with health and beauty being the primary uses. While beauty-related information is more commonly highlighted in Istanbul, in Bozdoğan, olive oil is more frequently used for health and traditional treatment methods.

- Olive oil is a very beneficial product, especially for cholesterol. Omega-3 is very beneficial for our bodies.
- “I use olive oil for my hair and eyelashes. It helps with the natural growth of eyelashes.
- "We use olive oil to soften our skin and also for fractures or dislocations in our bodies. It is very beneficial.
- Olive oil has many benefits for the skin. It softens the skin and prevents blemishes.